

Oral Presentation #55 was presented at the 3rd International Eastern Black Sea Family Medicine Congress, held in Ordu, Türkiye, on May 22–24, 2025, and is part of the proceedings titled: Proceedings of the 3rd International Eastern Black Sea Family Medicine Congress.

AUTHORS

Merve Günaydın
<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-9097-3211>

Kübra Aydın Bahat
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2620-9991>

AFFILIATIONS

Ordu University
Department of Family Medicine
Ordu, Turkey

Ordu University
Department of Nephrology
Ordu, Turkey

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Hypokalemia is a common electrolyte disturbance encountered in clinical practice, frequently caused by gastrointestinal losses or diuretic use.

Case Presentation: We present a case of a 42-year-old male who was admitted with diarrhea and muscle weakness, later diagnosed with Gitelman syndrome based on biochemical features including hypokalemia, hypomagnesemia, hypocalciuria, metabolic alkalosis, and increased urinary chloride excretion.

Discussion: Persistent or treatment-resistant hypokalemia should prompt further evaluation to identify rare causes such as inherited renal tubulopathies.

Conclusion: This case underscores the importance of considering Gitelman syndrome in the differential diagnosis of resistant hypokalemia.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Gitelman syndrome, hypokalemia, hypomagnesemia, metabolic alkalosis, renal tubulopathy

INTRODUCTION

Hypokalemia is a common electrolyte imbalance encountered in clinical practice. The most frequent causes include gastrointestinal losses such as diarrhea and vomiting. Other causes are inappropriate diuretic use, malignancies, and primary hyperaldosteronism. Resistant hypokalemia is defined as a serum potassium level remaining below 3.5 mmol/L despite appropriate replacement therapy. In this report, we present a case of resistant hypokalemia ultimately attributed to Gitelman syndrome, a rare tubulopathy (Fulchiero & Seo-Mayer, 2019).

CASE PRESENTATION

A 42-year-old male patient presented to the emergency department with complaints of diarrhea for three days, generalized weakness, and diffuse body aches. His general condition was good, and he was conscious and oriented. He had no known chronic illnesses and was not on any regular medication. On physical examination, respiratory sounds were normal bilaterally. Blood pressure was 100/60 mmHg, pulse 76 bpm, and his ECG showed sinus rhythm without pathological findings. Other systemic examinations were unremarkable.

Initial laboratory investigations revealed: Hgb: 16 g/dL, WBC: 11,000/mm³, Ca: 8.6 mg/dL, Na: 141 mmol/L, K: 2.5 mmol/L, creatinine: 1.2 mg/dL, Cl: 90 mmol/L, Mg: 1.28 mg/dL, CRP: 9.9 mg/L, TSH: 1.04 mIU/mL, T4: 1.3 ng/dL. Arterial blood gas analysis showed: pH: 7.5, HCO₃: 32.3 mmol/L, pCO₂: 43.7 mmHg, lactate: 1.6 mmol/L. Urinalysis revealed no signs of infection.

The patient was hospitalized in the internal medicine ward with a preliminary diagnosis of gastroenteritis and for further evaluation of hypokalemia. Intravenous isotonic fluids and potassium replacement therapy were initiated. Daily monitoring of renal function and electrolytes was performed. Despite the resolution of diarrhea by the second day, hypokalemia persisted. Spironolactone 50 mg was started along with 6 g of IV potassium over 6 hours. On the second day, potassium was 3.07 mmol/L, and potassium supplementation was continued. Oral potassium (1.56 g twice daily) and spironolactone were maintained.

On day three, serum potassium was 3.36 mmol/L. Spironolactone dose was increased to 100 mg, and magnesium and calcium supplementation was added. On day four, serum potassium dropped again to 3.0 mmol/L. Treatment was adjusted to spironolactone 100 mg/day, IV potassium 4 ampules/day, ramipril 2.5 mg/day, oral magnesium, potassium citrate (three times daily), and calcium carbonate-cholecalciferol (once daily). By day five, potassium levels reached 4.0 mmol/L, and IV potassium was discontinued with continuation of oral therapies.

ACTH and cortisol levels obtained at admission were 20.3 pg/mL and 429 nmol/L, respectively, and within normal ranges. Renin (1.88 ng/mL/h) and aldosterone (8.58 ng/dL) levels obtained before treatment were also within normal limits. A 24-hour urine analysis showed chloride: 255 mmol/day, phosphate: 381 mmol/day, calcium: 1.5 mg/day—consistent with hypocalciuria. Blood and urine cultures were negative, as was the stool culture obtained during hospitalization. Thoracic CT and abdominal/pelvic MRI with contrast showed no evidence of a neuroendocrine tumor.

DISCUSSION

This patient presented with symptoms suggestive of a gastrointestinal cause of hypokalemia, which was supported by the initial presence of diarrhea. However, the persistence of hypokalemia despite symptom resolution and potassium replacement necessitated further workup. After ruling out common causes such as Cushing's syndrome, hyperaldosteronism, and diuretic use, the constellation of findings -including hypomagnesemia, hypocalciuria, metabolic alkalosis, and high urinary chloride excretion- was highly suggestive of Gitelman syndrome (Parmar, Muppidi, & Bashir, 2024).

Gitelman syndrome is a rare inherited tubulopathy caused by mutations in the SLC12A3 gene, affecting the thiazide-sensitive sodium-chloride co-transporter in the distal convoluted tubule. It leads to excessive renal loss of potassium and magnesium, reduced calcium excretion, and secondary hyperaldosteronism. Unlike Bartter syndrome, Gitelman syndrome typically presents later in life and is associated with hypocalciuria and milder volume depletion.

Diagnosis is typically clinical, supported by characteristic biochemical abnormalities. Although genetic testing can confirm the diagnosis, it is not always necessary for treatment initiation. Management focuses on correcting electrolyte imbalances and includes oral potassium and magnesium supplementation, potassium-sparing diuretics such as spironolactone, and RAAS blockade via ACE inhibitors or ARBs (Cho et al., 2024). This case emphasizes the importance of considering rare renal tubular disorders such as Gitelman syndrome in patients with persistent or treatment-resistant hypokalemia. Prompt recognition and appropriate management can significantly improve symptoms and prevent complications. Gitelman syndrome, though uncommon, should be part of the differential diagnosis when facing unexplained hypokalemia, especially when accompanied by metabolic alkalosis, hypomagnesemia, and hypocalciuria.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

REFERENCES

Cho, M. H., Park, P. G., Kim, J. H., Jang, K. M., Lee, J. M., Yang, E. M., Park, S. J., Suh, J. S., Cho, H., Lee, J. W., Lee, J. H., Koo, J. W., Namgoong, M. K., Kim, K. H., Ahn, Y. H., Kang, H. G., & Cheong, H. I. (2024). Genotype-phenotype correlations in children with Gitelman syndrome. *Clinical and Experimental Nephrology*, 28(8), 803–810. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10157-024-02474-x>

Fulchiero, R., & Seo-Mayer, P. (2019). Bartter syndrome and Gitelman syndrome. *Pediatric Clinics of North America*, 66(1), 121–134. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pcl.2018.08.010>

Parmar, M. S., Muppidi, V., & Bashir, K. (2024). Gitelman syndrome. In *StatPearls*. StatPearls Publishing.
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK470215/>

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR

Merve Gunaydin

Ordu University

Department of Family Medicine

Ordu, Turkey

<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-9097-3211>

merve.yesilyurt@saglik.gov.tr